

Using DNN-based architecture in two stages for Scene Classification in multi-spectral EO

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Earth Observation (EO) applications are both advancing at an unbelievable pace. However, the use of AI in EO has its challenges, specially for DNN based techniques. Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) that form the basis of advanced DNN-based algorithms for automatic understanding of scenes in imagery data are conventionally meant to work on RGB images and, therefore, pose significant challenge when applying on Multispectral (MS) data. In this work, we present a two-stage approach to use Deep Neural Networks (DNN) architecture for Scene Classification in Copernicus Sentinel 2 data. Results shown here are focused on a specific scene i.e., Water. However, the approach is generic and can easily be extended to other scenes.

1 Introduction

Having proven its success in majority of computer vision application, DNN-based approaches have also seen unprecedented rise in the field of Earth Observation (EO) and Remote Sensing (RS) [1]. There are three main reasons for this – 1) The rise in the number of EO missions and, consequently, of the number of associated necessary applications. This also leads to a very large increase of EO data being readily available to contribute for EO science. 2) One of the main obstacle in the past to apply DNN based approaches in EO data was the lack of available hardware resources required by DL algorithms. This is no more an obstacle with the development of high-end processors and graphics card. 3) Lastly, Deep Neural Networks are advancing rapidly in Computer vision domain with results from latest models outperforming human vision at times, which is an implicit requirement when applying to EO science.

Automatic understanding of scenes in EO data is one of the topic in EO & RS, where DNN-based algorithms have found immense popularity. However, application of advanced DNN-based architectures (con-

taining Convolutional layer) are often limited to 3-channel input data such as Red, Green and Blue channel for scene classification. For a non-CNN deep architectures, often the contextual information is lost when trying to learn the label for a given input pixel. While Machine Learning (ML) methods [2] are easier for pixel-wise classification of MS data, CNN-based classifier are often complicated to adapt to MS imagery. There have been attempts to adapt CNN-based architecture for classification of MS data [3, 4] but with a limited depth of the architecture. This limits the architecture to learn complexities of image data. In another work [5], the authors show results from earlier state-of-art CNN-based models for multi-label classification at scene level. They have successfully trained some of the well-known models like DenseNet201 [6], ResNet50 [7] and slightly modified VGG10 [8] on 6-bands imagery data from Sentinel 2 (S2). Our goal was to employ advanced models that are specifically designed to overcome some of the short-comings such as multi-scale segmentation and learning of contextual information without losing resolution. Therefore, we chose one of the latest state-of-art DNN architecture, DeepLabv3 [6], which enables segmentation at multiple-scale. In addition, the goal is also to use the valuable features, not limited to RGB, within MS data from sources such as Sentinel satellite constellation, and NASA's LANDSAT mission. The extended range of MS data allows for the detection of features and phenomena that are not visible in RGB data, such as vegetation health, soil moisture, and mineral composition. We prove our approach using MS imagery from Sentinel 2, which comprises twin satellites (2A and 2B) capable of imaging in 13 different spectral bands, ranging from 443 nm to 2190 nm [9]. In the Sections below, we present a two-stage approach for automatic extraction of scenes in a given MS EO data – 1) In the first stage, we apply a pre-processing technique to identify all the relevant bands and merge them together to form various 3-band input features. 2) In the second stage, we train the feature bands,

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one model per feature bands and compare the results to select the best combination of feature bands and thereby, the best model. The work presented here is mainly focused on Water segmentation from Copernicus Sentinel 2 MS data [9] but can easily be extended to classify other scenes. This work builds on our earlier study [10], where we explored several preliminary approaches for water segmentation on Sentinel 2 data and discuss the main challenges of the task.

2 Approach

Scene classification from EO data can be described as Image Segmentation problem in Computer vision terminology. Inherently, most DNN-based architecture for Image is designed to process only RGB channels. In order to take advantage of the complex architecture of our selected model (DeepLabv3) enabling segmentation at multiple scale and at the same time to be able to use bands other than RGB, we came up with the following steps to train this model on multispectral bands – 1) Pre-processing - Analysis of individual bands and several combination of bands to finalize features that distinguishes water from the rest visually. 2) Modeling - Prepare input training data by adding pre-processing step as required and train individual models from various combination of significant bands. This results in several trained models which can be compared against test data for finalization.

2.1 First Stage - Pre-processing

In this stage, we evaluate all MS bands at 10m (B2, B3, B4) and 20m (B5, B6, B7, B8a, B11, B12) to select the bands capable of visually distinguishing Water areas from the rest. We experimented with various normalization techniques keeping in mind, also the requirement of DL layers. Selected bands were merged to form several 3-bands combination and visually inspected to finalize feature band combinations that can be used for training our models to extract water areas. We chose 20m input resolution since majority of bands produced by S2 are at 20m or higher. The pre-processing step for generating each of the resulting 4 datasets mainly consisted of normalizing the non-RGB band spectral indices in RGB range [0, 255] as follows –

$$Bx_{norm} = \frac{Bx * 255.0}{B_max} \quad (1)$$

where Bx is Band x , Bx_{norm} is the normalized value of band x and B_max is the global maximum value of Band x . Global maxima was computed from the 30 tiles chosen as a base to build our dataset (described

in 2.2.1 and Table 1) After normalization, the bands were merged and saved as a single 3D matrix of shape 549x549x3. In Figure 1, we visualize the normalized feature band B3, B5, B8A and B12 where one can see that these bands are capable of distinguishing water from non-water regions. Further in Figure 2, we show the combination of these feature bands that forms favorable input features to DeepLabv3 model for training our water segmentation model.

2.2 Second Stage - Modeling

Once the significant feature bands as well as possible combination of feature bands have been identified, we move to the modeling stage. This involves preparation of dataset and training of models, which are described in the sub-sections below.

2.2.1 Dataset

There is no known dataset freely available for this task. Therefore, we have prepared our own dataset in two steps - first, preparing RGB-only image patches and corresponding water masks followed by extension of this data to include pre-processed feature bands. Figure 4 shows how the final MS dataset was produced in two steps. For the first step, 30 S2-L1C TCI (True Color Image) down-sampled to 20m were selected to cover vast geographical regions containing as many variants of data as possible including river, sea, ocean and lakes. To generate corresponding water masks, spectral-indices¹ based Water Mapping algorithm was applied to these 30 S2 products - Output pixel is labelled water where $NDWI > 0$ and $S2WI > 0.1$. These were further divided into patches of smaller size (549x549) and good matches (TCI patch and Water mask) were manually filtered (by visual inspection) using the following removal criteria –

- Water masks having high number of misclassified pixels.
- Most image patches not having water content.
- Images containing large areas covered by clouds and cirrus.

It shall be noted that not all bad patches were removed. However, manual filtering was essential to balance the dataset so that model can learn target feature well. At the same time, we can assume that there is also noise in the dataset from pixel-wise classification inaccuracies of spectral-indices based algorithm. Our final dataset consisted of 1578 samples (see Table 1).

¹<https://awesome-ee-spectral-indices.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

Figure 1: S2 Bands B3, B5, B8A, B12 normalized showing significant difference from the rest of the features and therefore makes for a good features for water segmentation task.

Figure 2: Shows several combination of significant bands that can be given as inputs to DeepLabv3 model for training a water segmentation model.

Figure 3 shows an example of image patch and corresponding Water Map from this dataset. Data samples for modelling was further appended by adding feature bands identified in stage 1, resulting in 4 different datasets of following band combinations – 1) B3B5B8a 2) B3B8aB12 3) B5B8aB12 4) B3B5B12

No. of tiles	No. of patches	No. of patches after filtering	Training samples	Validation samples
30	3000	1578	1263	315

Table 1: Water Segmentation Dataset summary.

Figure 3: Image patch (left) and the corresponding Water Map (right)

Figure 4: Water segmentation dataset produced in 2 stages – (a) RGB-based data from visual inspection and manual filtering followed by (b) extension of RGB dataset by appending additional bands at 20m keeping the patch indices consistent.

2.2.2 Models training and finalization

For modelling, DeepLabv3 [6] is our preferred DNN-based architecture as it is one of the recent state-of-art method that handles the problem of object segmentation at multiple scales by employing atrous convolution in cascade or in parallel. This is achieved by

Figure 5: Image from DeepLabv3 paper explaining how Atrous convolution with $rate > 1$ enlarges the model’s field of view and enables object encoding at multiple scale.

employing atrous convolution in parallel and at multiple rates (strides) as shown in Figure 5. This model also takes into account the contextual information of a given pixel because at the base of it are CNNs and atrous convolution.

DeepLabv3 models were trained using the above 4 pre-processed datasets. The loss and accuracy curve for each of the models is shown in Figure 6. It can be seen from the plots that all 4 models were able to reach the accuracy $> 98\%$ for train and validation sets and at the same time loss could be minimized below 0.1.

3 Results & Discussion

We have evaluated these models on various tiles and show the results on one specific use-case in Figure 7. Results point to model trained on B3B5B8a as the best model for macro-area segmentation whereas models trained on B5B8aB12 for micro-area segmentation. Figure 9 show results on two different S2 tiles further validating the accuracy of our model trained on B3B5B8a. To better understand the performance of the models trained on selected feature bands, we have also compared the results with the same model trained on RGB bands (B4B3B2). Figure 8 shows one of the problem area, where RGB (B4B3B2) trained model failed to generalize on areas where the color of water is unconventional due to sedimentation and other external factors. Even though the approach above is explained using Water segmentation example, it can very well be extended for other scenes as well. The results show that advanced DNN-based architectures when trained on pre-processed MS images (not necessarily RGB) have great potential in extracting complicated scenes from Sentinel 2 data, which

might not be possible when using only RGB images or MS pixel-wise classification. Our future work includes application of this approach to classify further scenes such as Forest, vegetation and non-vegetation areas on Sentinel 2 and other EO data.

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Figure 6: Loss and Accuracy curves from different training of DeepLabv3 model on different band combinations.

Figure 7: Water masks generated from deeplabv3 models trained on several 3-band feature combination. From the outputs, one can see that models trained on B3B5B8a, B3B8aB12 and B5B8aB12 performs well with B3B8aB12 model being able to segment macro-areas better than others and B5B8aB12 model being able to segment micro-areas better than others.

Figure 8: Inference on full tile (T36RVU, 06.08.2023) from a DeepLabv3 trained model on RGB (B4B3B2) data. While the model performs well on generating water mask for regions that resembles water (in terms of color) but gets confused in other areas where the color of water is unconventional due to sedimentation and other external factors. The miss-classified regions can be seen within the red outline.

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Figure 9: Further results from our preferred model trained on B3B5B8a bands.